

3D Printed Smart Luminous Artifacts

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Abstract. The Additive Manufacturing (AM) industry is investing more and more in 3D Printing, which has opened new paths and opportunities in the field of Smart Manufacturing, providing previously unfathomable technological innovations in every sector. This paper presents a robust methodology approach to empower users through low-cost and Do-It-Yourself activities for rapid prototyping of Smart Luminous Artifacts using different AM technologies as follows: a) Stereolithography (SLA) was used for the fabrication of the 3D printed transparent artifact which is printed using optical transparent resin, b) multi-functional ink-jet circuit printing using silver nanoparticle inks on plastic substrates for producing hybrid Printed Circuit Boards (PCB) with unique geometry and interconnect architecture with various levels of component embedding, and c) Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) technology for printing the electronics housing. In the case of the printed PCB electrodes, a process optimization study was performed at annealing temperatures of 180, 200, 220°C for 30 minutes. The macro- and micro-morphology of the PCB printed electrodes were investigated by Stereo-Microscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) respectively, while the printed electrode thickness was calculated by exploiting auto-focus track tool of inVia Raman Spectroscopy. The customised 3D printed parts were assembled under simplicity and low power consumption, to create the 3D printed Smart Luminous Artifacts, which are combined with advanced IoT functionalities in order to be controllable via Wi-Fi and Bluetooth by a user-friendly mobile application. This methodology approach is ideal for being followed by educators in high schools, colleges and universities to train the students and engineers on co-creation and co-design using digital manufacturing technologies.

Keywords: Additive Manufacturing, PCB, Do-It-Yourself, Smart Systems, IoT.

1 Introduction

Social manufacturing is associated with the maker and Do-It-Yourself (DIY) movement [1]. Social manufacturing is characterized by the systematic utilization of the power of

communities to design and manufacture high personalized goods and is strongly associated with point of need manufacturing and production via additive manufacturing technologies [1]. Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies, such as 3D printing, have been gaining attention since their emerging around 1985 [2], and have been developing side by side with state-of-the-art concepts the last years in Industry 4.0 [3] and IoT applications [4], by becoming a solid part not only in research, but also in industry on a global scale. By utilizing manufacturing methods, such as the abovementioned, it is possible to design and produce functional prototypes based on customized and personalized needs and dynamic requirements. Additionally, AM offer the option of changing the model's characteristics and reprinting it until it reaches the desired form, without having to standardize the process, but instead enabling the creation of custom products with each print. Combining a 3D printed model with IoT functionalities in custom designs are a fixture in our daily lives, providing sensing, human-computer interaction, and communication in single smart personalized devices and applications in industry.

This study is motivated solely by the need to assess on-demand, highly flexible digital manufacturing with optimum quality based on a robust methodology for creating 3D printed smart prototypes. Adjustments towards the optimization of the printing processes were conducted, considering Stereolithography (SLA), Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) and PCB Inkjet Printing, focusing mostly on the latest which requires to achieve the operational functionality of the prototype's electronics.

2 Methodology and Approach

In order to enhance Do-it- Yourself communities and various other innovation players to collaborate with other identified stakeholders under co-creation and sharing economy, a flexible methodology approach for creating 3D Printed Smart Luminous Artifacts has been designed.

Initially, the conceptual definition of the systemic innovative prototype and its components' specifications and requirements, on mechanical and optical properties, accuracy, size, schema, conductivity and type of material are identified. It follows the phase for defining the 3D CAD design of each individual component that constitutes the prototype in systemic innovation. In this study, the three main components of the 3D Printed Smart Luminous Artifact that was selected for demonstration, were manufactured with different appropriate low-cost printing processes as deployed and analyzed in the following sub-sections 2.1-2.3. The optimization procedure mainly in the development of the hybrid PCB is crucial for the operational performance and functionality of the printed IoT systemic prototype. Thus, state-of-the-art analytical methods and tools for characterization have to be applied. At last, PCB programming and assembling of the customized 3D printed parts under simplicity and low power consumption are required, to create the final 3D printed Smart Luminous Artifact prototype that can be controllable via Wi-Fi or Bluetooth by a user-friendly mobile application.

2.1 Design & Manufacturing of a Hybrid PCB by Multi-Functional Ink-Jet Circuit Printing

The inkjet printing technology utilizes the method of 2-dimensional deposition of conductive ink on several substrates (plastic, paper, glass etc.), following a calculated path based on the designed circuitry, which needs to be depicted on the substrate. The parameters of the printing process rely on the conductive ink properties, such as the density, viscosity, melting point, conductivity etc. The selection of optimal values for each of the printing and annealing parameters plays a consequential role on the quality of the final prototype, affecting the circuitry as a whole, due to its fundamental functionality as a complete part, since the conductive ink creates the electrodes which connect the electronics and work as a path for the current.

In this study, a multi-functional ink-jet circuit printing system (Voltera V-One) was used for the fabrication of the printed electrodes of the hybrid PCB on plastic substrates, utilizing a commercial silver nanoparticle ink.

To achieve optimal results regarding the conductivity and continuity of the printed PCB electrodes, a series of experiments was conducted for optimization of the printing process during the annealing procedure. The process optimization study includes the fabrication of a number of printed Ag NP electrodes on FR1 plastic substrates at different annealing temperatures at 180, 200, 220°C for 30 minutes. The macro- and micro-morphology of the printed electrodes were investigated by Stereo-Microscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) respectively, while the printed traces thickness was calculated by exploiting auto-focus track tool of inVia Ra-man Spectroscopy. The findings of the macro- and micro-morphology optimization study revealed (more details in section 3), that the printed Ag NP electrodes which were annealed at 200°C exhibit the most homogenous uniformity and continuity as well as the lowest resistance values, compared with samples annealed at 180°C and 220°C for the same time duration.

In **Fig. 1**, the homogeneity and continuity of the optimum Ag NP Ink electrode annealed at 200°C is revealed by a simple HD image obtained by a Leica DMS1000 stereo-microscope.

Fig. 1. Ag NP printed electrode with optimal process parameters at 200°C/30 min.

Having acquired the printing (droplet size $850\mu\text{m}$, print height $70\mu\text{m}$) and optimum annealing parameters ($200^\circ\text{C}/30\text{ min}$) for the fabrication of the Ag NP electrodes, the circuitry of the PCB was developed. In particular, the PCB layout design (Fig. 2a) was implemented using KiCad Software and exported in Gerber file format (.gbr). The exported .gbr format was inserted to the Voltera V-One software and the printed Ag NP electrodes were fabricated on a plastic FR1 substrate according to the selected optimal manufacturing parameters. The development of the hybrid PCB (Fig. 2b) was completed by embedding the electronic components using a T5 - Sn63Pb37 solder paste. The circuit is designed to combine high efficiency with low energy consumption. Therefore, a low energy RGB LED WS2812b ($V_o=5\text{V}$) was selected to be controlled with a low power microprocessor ESP32 WROOM-32D (MCU & Wi-Fi & Bluetooth module - $V_o=3.3\text{V}$). Finally, the fabricated hybrid PCB enables the integration of a USB Port for power supply and a battery with 12 hours autonomy ($I_o=160\sim 260\text{mA}$) for convenience.

Fig. 2. a) PCB layout design and b) ITI-CERTH hybrid PCB

2.2 Design & Manufacturing of the Electronics Housing –by Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF)

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) or Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) is an extrusion-based AM technology and currently the most widespread in the market, because of its simplicity, low cost and material accessibility. The materials used in FFF are mainly thermoplastics in the form of a filament, which is liquified by applying heat so that it can be deposited through a nozzle on the printing bed in a layer-by-layer manner.

In this specific case the material selected for 3D Printing the electronics housing was a Polylactic acid (PLA) filament of 1.75mm diameter, a lightweight, recyclable and biodegradable material which is very easy to find, while it also provides good mechanical properties, such as strength and durability, in order to protect the electronics which are going to be placed inside. A Prusa FFF printer was used to fabricate the electronics housing, which was designed via Solidworks™ software program, according the specifications and requirements of artifact and hybrid PCB on size and schema. The printing process parameters which led to the optimal fabrication of the electronics housing were

0.2mm for layer thickness, 15% infill, printing temperature 210°C and 80mm/s for printing speed.

2.3 Prototyping & Testing

Last step of the proposed methodology and approach is the assembling of the individual printing components and the functionality testing (**Fig. 3**). Once the hybrid PCB has been examined for short circuiting or voltage drops/energy losses, it necessary to check if it functions correctly using a robust mobile application (AMU4you), which was designed by ITI-CERTH especially for this specific smart device, with a user-friendly interface and simplicity. More analytically, all the functions of the RGB LED light were tested, including the change in color, brightness and blinking pattern, as well as the connectivity between the application and the circuit. The application connects with the microprocessor of the hybrid PCB by identifying its IP address (added by the user), and can adjust the behavior of the RGB LED light by selecting a specific activity or manually, using Bluetooth or through the Wi-Fi network.

Fig. 3. Assembly and Testing of Prototype

3 Results & Discussion

For the optimization of the printed PCB electrodes fabrication a thoroughly study on annealing procedure has been performed. The printed Ag NP electrodes on FR1 substrates were annealed at 180, 200 and 220°C for 30 minutes respectively, to study the effect of temperature and post thermal curing duration.

Figure 4.a and 4b depicts the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-5600V) images of the electrodes cured at 180°C and 220°C, exhibiting similar surface morphology for the two samples, that have been treated to the minimum and maximum temperature and duration respectively. Using a digital multimeter, the resistance found for both samples $\sim 0.2\Omega$. All electrodes exhibited similar morphology due to the sintering of Ag NP over 175°C [5]; the sintered Ag nanoparticles aggregated to larger irregular schemes, with sizes from 10nm to 3 μ m. The connectivity of the sintered Ag particulates attributes to the electrode the final conductivity coherence.

Fig. 4. Surface morphological characterization by SEM of electrode cured at (a) 180°C/ 20 min and (b) 220°C/ 60 min, (c) cross section of 200°C/ 20 min and (d) in Via microscopy image by $\times 10$ lens at PCB focus ($z=0$) and electrode focus ($z=57$)

Sample 200°C min was cut and placed in epoxy resin to study the cross-section of the electrode, as exhibited in Figure 4c. The cross section showed homogeneous sintering of the Ag NP over the z axis, in accordance to the conductivity measurements. The thickness of the electrode was homogeneous and was 57 μm according to the SEM image scale. An automated and non-destructive method was developed by in Via Raman spectroscopy for the measurement of the electrode thickness. The automated sample tray of the instrument can detect with sub-micron resolution any movement over the x, y and z axis. $Z=0$ was set on the PCB close to the electrode, as exhibited on Figure 4d, while the auto-focus tool of the Wire 5.3 Renishaw software can automatically focus on a selected point by the optimum spectra quality, thus calculating the electrode thickness at 57 μm . The respective method was performed on various points of the electrode, measuring automatically and with micrometer resolution the thickness values. The resistance measurements for the sample 200°C min performed by a digital multimeter have shown $<0.1\Omega$, an electrical value that agrees with the characterization results for the macro- and micro-morphology.

4 Conclusions

The 3D Printed Smart Luminous Artifact was developed in order to encourage co-creational Do-It-Yourself activities by implementing low-cost Additive Manufacturing

technologies to a systemic innovative design. The methodology approach which was presented in this study enables educators and non-professional users to create their own customized smart devices, reinforcing Design Thinking and introducing the concept of Smart Manufacturing under the growing trend of personalization and socialization.

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